

ANALYTICAL APPROACHES TO THE RUDYARD KIPLING'S POETRY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13324852>

Abstract. Rudyard Kipling's poetry, renowned for its vivid imagery and rhythmic versatility, offers a profound exploration of imperialism, adventure, and human nature. This article delves into Kipling's thematic concerns, including his complex portrayal of British imperialism and the nuanced depiction of diverse cultures. By analyzing key works such as "If—," "The Law of the Jungle," and "The way through the woods," the study highlights Kipling's use of mythic structures, moral allegories, and narrative techniques to address themes of duty, resilience, and identity. Additionally, it examines how Kipling's personal experiences and historical context influenced his poetic vision. Through a critical lens, the article seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of Kipling's contributions to poetry and his impact on literary traditions and cultural perceptions of his time.

Key words: R. Kipling, literature, poetry, prose, narrative technique, didactic tone, traditional folklore, character.

Rudyard Kipling is one of the best-known of the late Victorian poets and story-tellers. Although he was awarded the Nobel Prize for literature in 1907, his political views, which grew more toxic as he aged, have long made him critically unpopular. Few poets are more beloved by more people than Rudyard Kipling. A favorite of readers both young and old, known the world over, Rudyard Kipling's poems – and stories – have proven both popular and evergreen.

Born Joseph Rudyard Kipling in 1865, Kipling was the son of Britons born in Bombay, India. At the age of five, young Kipling was sent to England to be educated, a traumatic experience that marked his childhood. Uncomfortable in England, Kipling returned to India as soon as he was able, at the age of 17. Kipling's first – and only job – was as a writer, beginning as a journalist and editor for a magazine for Britons living in India.

In 1886, Kipling's first collection of poetry, *Departmental Ditties and Other Verses* was published. Only two years later, he published his first book of prose, *Plain Tales from the Hills*.

In the early 1890s, Kipling gained worldwide fame with the publication of *Barrack-Room Ballad*, in which were two of his most famous poems, the exotic "Gunga Din" and "Mandalay." These poems brought the experience of Britons in

India to the world at large, and only encouraged Kipling to continue to write poems and stories about India, tales and verses of adventure that brought a country unknown to most to readers worldwide.

Kipling married in 1892 and left his beloved India for Vermont, where he continued his fascination with India by writing the two Jungle Books and Kim. For several years he traveled the world, both with his family and alone, spending the Boer War in South Africa, continuing to publish both prose and poetry, including the novel Captains Courageous and Just-So Stories.

In 1901, Kipling and his family settled in Sussex, England, permanently. While in Sussex, Kipling wrote many poems and stories, among them his best-known poem, "If."

Rudyard Kipling died on January 18, 1936. At the time of his death, he was one of the most famous and beloved authors of his time. From the whimsy and humor of Just-So Stories to the adventure of "Gunga-Din" to the stately advice of "If," Rudyard Kipling's writing has proven to be timeless, and still fascinates and delights children and adults alike.

Kipling's writing is characterized by its realism, its vivid portrayal of British India, and its exploration of themes of imperialism, duty, and the clash of cultures. He was a master of storytelling, and his works continue to be read and enjoyed by people of all ages.

Kipling's work is often discussed alongside that of other writers of the Victorian and Edwardian eras, such as Charles Dickens, Thomas Hardy, and Joseph Conrad. These authors were all concerned with exploring the complexities of the modern world, and their work reflects the social, political, and economic changes that were taking place during their lifetimes. Kipling's focus on British Imperialism, however, makes his work distinct from these other authors. He is considered a significant literary figure, though certain aspects of his work remain controversial to this day.

Rudyard Kipling's poetry, including 'If,' is known for its didactic and moralistic tone. His poetry often imparts life lessons and wisdom, aiming to guide readers towards ethical and virtuous behavior. Many people consider 'If—' to be one of the most inspirational poems ever written. It is certainly a poem that has garnered a great deal of attention in popular culture. "If" exemplifies Kipling's style, offering a set of values and virtues to be embraced as a guide to navigate life's challenges. His poetry is characterized by its directness and clarity, presenting concise and impactful messages. 'If' is without a doubt his best-known poem and his most commonly studied.

If you can keep your head when all about you
Are losing theirs and blaming it on you;
If you can trust yourself when all men doubt you,
But make allowance for their doubting too:
If you can wait and not be tired by waiting,
Or, being lied about, don't deal in lies,
Or being hated don't give way to hating,...

This poem emphasizes the importance of maintaining composure, integrity, and determination in the face of adversity. The speaker presents a series of challenges and tests, urging the reader to endure them with resilience and dignity.

Compared to Kipling's other works, such as "The Jungle Book" and "The Man Who Would Be King," this poem is more introspective and philosophical. It reflects the author's experiences in the British Empire, where he witnessed both the best and worst of human nature. The poem's focus on character and integrity aligns with the Victorian era's emphasis on duty, self-reliance, and the importance of the individual. It provides a timeless guide for navigating life's challenges with strength, perseverance, and humility.

Another poem "The Law of the Jungle" by Rudyard Kipling succinctly outlines the hierarchical social structure and behavioral code of the animal kingdom. It emphasizes the importance of unity, loyalty, and respect within the pack, and adherence to ancient traditions. The poem's didactic tone is reminiscent of traditional folklore, conveying practical wisdom and moral guidelines.

Now this is the Law of the Jungle — as old and as true as the sky; And the Wolf that shall keep it may prosper, but the Wolf that shall break it must die.

As the creeper that girdles the tree-trunk the Law runneth forward and back
-For the strength of the Pack is the Wolf, and the strength of the Wolf is the Pack.

This poem focuses more on the abstract principles of jungle society rather than specific characters or adventures. Its concise and structured language creates a sense of authority and timelessness. In the context of its time period, this poem reflects the Victorian fascination with nature and the romanticization of the wild. It also aligns with the prevailing social norms and emphasis on order and discipline.

The poem "The way through the woods" explores the hidden nature of the past, using the forgotten road as a metaphor for lost memories and forgotten histories. The imagery of the now overgrown road suggests that time and nature can conceal the past, even as traces of it remain visible to those who know where to look.

They shut the road through the woods
Seventy years ago.
Weather and rain have undone it again,
And now you would never know
There was once a road through the woods
Before they planted the trees.
It is underneath the coppice and heath,
And the thin anemones.
Only the keeper sees
That, where the ring-dove broods,
And the badgers roll at ease,
There was once a road through the woods.

The poem's structure reinforces this theme, with the first stanza establishing the road's former existence and its subsequent disappearance. The second stanza then evokes the possibility that the road still exists in some form, accessible only to those who are attuned to its secrets.

This poem differs from Kipling's other works, which often celebrate the British Empire and its military prowess. Instead, it focuses on the more subtle and elusive aspects of history and memory. It also reflects the growing sense of nostalgia and loss that characterized the late Victorian era in England.

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